

SELF-HEALING AND STRENGTH RECOVERY EVALUATION OF SUPER ABSORBENT POLYMERS CONCRETE MIXES UNDER CONTROLLED DAMAGE

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ABSTRACT

The durability of concrete is invariably a challenge for engineers and material technologists due to the frequent maintenance and service required on concrete structures and infrastructures hence resulting in economical deficiency. Concrete healing innovations have been developed over the past decade; these various technologies for concrete self-healing include biotechnological, polymeric and chemical compounds. Super absorbent polymers are considered as a progressive method to deliver the water content into the cementitious matrix and stimulate hydration and in situ carbonation of cementitious materials. This study investigates the effect of super absorbent polymer addition into the cementitious materials and the efficiency of concrete crack healing and recovery of mechanical properties from cracks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is the most favourable material used in the construction industry due its production process, raw material availability, affordability and recyclability [1]. Divergently, it is the tensile characteristics of concrete that causes cracking probability [2] which compromises the durability of concrete [3]. The development of micro-cracks in the cementitious matrix is the result of hydration and volumetric variation (i.e. thermal contraction, shrinkage in fresh and hardened concrete), environmental conditions (freezing and thawing) and mechanical loadings (static or dynamic). The formed micro-cracks are extremely difficult to be detected and can lead to the formation of macro-sized cracks [4]. In reinforced concrete, undesirable fluid and gas transport through these cracks can lead to corrosion of steel reinforcement and potential failure of concrete structures [5, 6]. Repairing micro-cracks in a cementitious matrix using the conventional methods could be extremely difficult and expensive. Concrete self-healing is one of the most promising methods for repairing these cracks, autonomously.

Super Absorbent Polymers (SAPs) is a technological material also utilized for concrete self-healing purposes. SAPs are cross-linked polymers and can absorb significant amounts of liquid in the surrounded environment and expand up to 500 times of their size [7]. This swelling capacity property proposes SAP as an additive in cementitious materials that carries water into the cementitious matrix and stimulates the cement hydration and in situ carbonation; however, during the release of the absorbed water, the dry SAP shrinks and reverses to its original dimension [4]. This mechanism of liquid provision and self-shrinkage of SAPs influences crack sealing and crack filling [8].

Researchers have used super absorbent polymers in various methods to propose crack healing and partial recovery of mechanical properties in cementitious materials. Kim and Schlangen [9] deployed SAPs with PVA-based ECC in the mortar mixture for crack width reduction and healing; SAPs content of 0.5% and 1.0% to the weight of cement were considered. After curing for 28 days, the four-point bending test was adopted to develop cracks and an average of 17.3 μm and 15.67 μm in crack width was obtained with respect to the SAP content (0.5 and 1%, respectively) compared to 22.3 μm for the control mix. After additional 28 days, samples were tested to failure by using a four-point bending test and it was concluded that the healing samples developed additional flexural strength and less deflection compared to the control samples. Sneek et al. [8] used SAP (cross-linked Potassium salt polyacrylate, particle size of $476.6 \pm 52.9 \mu\text{m}$) of 1%, 2% and 4% with respect to the cement weight and 2% by volume of PVA for all mixes. After 28 days, cracks were again developed by using the four-point bending method with crack width of 100-150 μm . Samples were cured under wet and dry cycles for additional 28 days and a four-point bending test to failure was finally conducted. It was observed that cracks' width up to 138 μm was healed for all SAP contents with 100% healing for SAP content of 2% and 4%; a strength reduction of 50% for 4% SAP and strength increment of 20% for 2% SAP was also observed. Gruraert et al. [10] added the in-house fabricated SAP with particle size less than 400 μm and 0.5% and 1% content by weight of cement, and achieved an increment of flexural strength of 8% and 6%, respectively; a general reduction of compressive strength for all SAP mixes was also noticed. The present study investigates the effect of Super Absorbent Polymers in the concrete mix without the addition of superplasticizer, micro-fibres and excessive water content. The analysis was carried out using X-Ray tomography for internal micro-porosity and cracking evaluation as well as standard mechanical tests and non-destructive tests for recovery assessment of mechanical properties.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 MATERIALS

General purpose cement (equivalent to CEM-I-42.5R) and local aggregates with nominal size of 7.0 mm, 10.0 mm, sand and water were used for the mixing process. Super absorbent polymers (FlosetTM 27CS) with particle size less than 500 μm were purchased from SNF Pty Ltd Australia.

2.2 SAMPLE PREPARATION AND CURING

Concrete specimens were fabricated with addition of SAPs; the concrete mix consisted of water to cement and sand to cement ratio of 0.54 and 1.83, respectively and nominal aggregate size of 7 mm and 10 mm with ratio of 0.8 and 1.61 to the weight of cement (PC CEM-I-42.5R) with addition of 1% (by cement weight) of SAPs. Cylindrical samples were casted as per AS 1012.8.1-14 [11] with diameter of 100 mm and height of 200 mm and a vibrating table was used for concrete compaction at 50Hz. Sample were kept at controlled conditions for 24 hours before de-moulding; they were then immersed in water for 28 days. Later, samples were cured in water to the completion of the experiment.

2.3 CRACK DEVELOPMENT

After 28 days of wet curing, samples were removed and dried at ambient conditions for two hours. Three replicates were tested to obtain the maximum compression strength at 28 days. A

self-synthesised steel mould was used to generate internal crack patterns; the mould consisted of two halved semi-circular sections with open ends at top and bottom sections. The semi-circular sections were connected by bolts and nuts. Cracks were developed by placing the concrete specimens into the self-synthesised mould and locating cylindrical steel plates at both opened ends. The steel mould with the concrete sample was positioned in the MTS-1000 kN machine between loading platens and an axial force was applied to induce axial circumferential pressure on the samples. Cracks were thus developed throughout the entire volume of the sample. Cracks were triggered by applying 40% and 70% of the maximum compressive strength as per initial measurement at 28 days.

2.4 METHODS OF TESTING

Ultrasonic Velocity Pulse and compression tests were conducted on concrete samples with SAPs for mechanical properties recovery while X-ray micro-tomography was undertaken for healing efficiency and change in porosity due to cracking. The three test types were performed at various time intervals after damaging the sample, including the 0, 3, 7, 14 and 28 days post 28 days of curing. All samples were labelled and Ultrasonic Velocity Pulse (UVP) was used to determine the dynamic modulus of concrete before the damaging procedure occurred as well as for each individual time interval (e.g. after being damaged).

Bruker SkyScan 1275 X-Ray micro-tomograph was used to obtain the porosity variation due to the formed cracks as well as to evaluate cracks development during healing. Concrete samples with diameter of 55 mm and 67 mm in height were placed on the micro-positioning stage of the instrument. The X-ray micro-tomograph was set to its maximum capacity with X-ray source of 100 kV tube voltage and 100 μ A tube current; for a superior transmission of x-ray through concrete and to obtain minimum noise level, a 1 mm copper film was placed between the x-ray source and concrete sample. The intensity of the x-ray beam transferred through concrete sample is attenuated due to concrete density and the detector receives the residual intensity hence the 2D image is produced [12]. At 0.2-degree rotation around its axis and resolution of 1540x1540 a total of 1535 images with 35 μ m thickness were obtained. Based on the 2D images, a 3D object reconstruction was obtained and data on internal porosity and crack development were collected.

3.0 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 DYNAMIC STIFFNESS

In this experiment, non-destructive tests were conducted to obtain the dynamic modulus of concrete. Ultrasonic Velocity Pulse was used to determine the pressure wave velocity passing through concrete samples. Then, according to ASTM C597-16 [13], Poisson's ratio of 0.15 and obtained average density of 1878.4 kg/m³ the stiffness of concrete was calculated. In figure 1, the dynamic modulus of the concrete with SAPs is shown at different curing times in comparison to the dynamic modulus of the concrete before cracking development.

Figure 1: Dynamic modulus of samples after damage and healing effect with time

3.2 COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

After internal micro-cracks were generated in all concrete samples, MTS-1000 kN compression machine was used to obtain the maximum axial force at failure; three replicates for each data set were measured. Figure 2 shows the compressive strength at each time interval after damage for 40% and 70% controlled crack development in comparison to the maximum compression strength prior to crack generation.

Figure 2: Residual and regain of compressive strength due to healing

3.3 MICRO CT-SCAN ANALYSIS

Micro CT scan tomography was used to analyse the induced porosity in the concrete samples due to damage. The operation involves analysing each 2D image based on the possible grey levels of intensity and the separation of air (voids and cracks) and solid phases. Air pores are dark grey due to lighter density hence less attenuation in translated intensity[14]. To determine the porosity of damaged samples by 40% and 70% in comparison to the control samples, the optimum of 44-255 grey level was applied throughout the entire campaign for consistency of results. Noise was reduced to the minimum level by applying global thresholding algorithm to convert the image to binary grey-scale image followed by the application of Otsu's method [14] to further separate the pore and solid phases. Also, black speckles smaller than 60 voxels were removed to obtain minimum noise level. Figure 3 shows the porosity at each time interval of 40% and 70% crack control damaged samples in comparison to control samples.

Figure 3: Porosity at various damage levels with respect to time

4.0 DISCUSSION

The efficiency of the addition of SAPs solely in a concrete mix for the purpose of crack healing and mechanical properties recovery was evaluated by utilizing non-destructive test methods and standard mechanical testing. It should be noted that the overall mechanical performance of the mix itself was not of interest to this research but rather was the effect of SAP on triggering concrete healing. Figure 1 shows the trend in stiffness of the concrete with SAPs. Prior to damage (and after 28 days of curing), the dynamic modulus of concrete was 10.8 GPa while right after being damaged at 40% and 70% of the maximum compressive strength, samples showed reduced stiffness of 5.44 GPa and 5.87 GPa, respectively. A regain in stiffness, thus increase in the velocity of ultrasonic pulses, was observed in both cases with almost full recovery (10.3 GPa for 70%-damage specimens and 9.6 GPa for 40%-damaged specimens) as per UPV assessment.

In this experiment the compressive strength and dynamic modulus results are generally lower than the standard concrete due to the inclusion of SAPs – absorbing water - without any extra water in the mix; hence less hydration in the cementitious matrix. Though the analysis of compressive strength results has suggested a partial strength regain with greater variability was observed among replicates. Both damaged samples exhibited an upward trend in the capacity of regaining strength with time although the 40%-damage specimens were not capable of fully recover from damage to their initial strength. This may be due to the different crack size generated by the damaging procedure.

Porosity content determination and crack healing efficiency was also estimated by utilizing X-ray tomography. Prior to damage, internal void content was 14.3%, which is generally higher than standard concrete although this could have been expected since no extra water or superplasticiser were used at this stage. Their addition is part of an ongoing research.

After being damaged, samples experienced an initial increase in porosity up to 15% and 15.5% for 40% and 70% damage, respectively. However, in both cases, a reduction of the internal void content was found with time although this was more gradual in the 40%-damaged samples.

Generally, 40%-damaged specimens needed more time to recover after being damaged; this suggests that there could be a close relationship between the healing efficiency of SAP and the size of the crack, which deserves more investigation.

CONCLUSION

The addition of super absorbent polymers in concrete proved to be beneficial in promoting healing phenomena; the efficiency of healing, though, followed different trends depending on the internal damage being generated in the samples. Non-destructive methods, such as UPV and X-ray, showed to capture well the internal micro-structure before and after damage.

Compared to other studies where healing efficiency is evaluated on a single crack generated by different form of flexural tests (or by a small group of cracks within a restricted area in the proximity of the maximum stress point), the present research developed a methodology to induce cracking patterns inside the entire volume of the sample. This approach, although still at an early stage, can prove to fit well in the assessment of healing.

Finally, the swelling capacity of super absorbent polymers enable them to be used in cementitious materials for delivering stored water into cementitious matrix hence stimulating cement hydration and crack healing.

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